

Flexible Generation Architecture for Current Transformers Testing up to 150 kHz

Gabriella Crotti
*Istituto Nazionale di Ricerca
Metrologica (INRIM)*
Turin, Italy
g.crotti@inrim.it

Giovanni D'Avanzo
*Ricerca sul Sistema Energetico
(RSE) S.p.A.*
Milan, Italy
giovanni.davanzo@rse-web.it

Antonio Delle Femine
*University of Campania "Luigi
Vanvitelli"*
Aversa (CE), Italy
antonio.dellefemine@unicampania.it

Daniele Gallo
*University of Campania "Luigi
Vanvitelli"*
Aversa (CE), Italy
daniele.gallo@unicampania.it

Domenico Giordano
*Istituto Nazionale di Ricerca
Metrologica (INRIM)*
Turin, Italy
d.giordano@inrim.it

Claudio Iodice
*University of Campania "Luigi
Vanvitelli"*
Aversa (CE), Italy
claudio.iodice@unicampania.it

Carmine Landi
*University of Campania "Luigi
Vanvitelli"*
Aversa (CE), Italy
carmine.landi@unicampania.it

Palma Sara Letizia
*Istituto Nazionale di Ricerca
Metrologica (INRIM)*
Turin, Italy
p.letizia@inrim.it

Mario Luiso
*University of Campania "Luigi
Vanvitelli"*
Aversa (CE), Italy
mario.luiso@unicampania.it

Daniele Palladini
*Ricerca sul Sistema Energetico
(RSE) S.p.A.*
Milan, Italy
daniele.palladini@rse-web.it

Davide Signorino
*Istituto Nazionale di Ricerca
Metrologica (INRIM)*
Turin, Italy
d.signorino@inrim.it

Abstract— High-Frequency Distortion (HFD) in both Low Voltage (LV) and Medium Voltage (MV) grids is gaining growing interest from the scientific and technical community due to its increasing occurrence and the issues they cause. Furthermore, the phenomenon of HFD is expected to rise as it primarily stems from newly installed devices essential for achieving decentralized generation from renewable sources. To monitor HFD in MV grids, the use of Instrument Transformers (ITs) is essential to scale down voltages and currents to levels compatible with the input stages of Power Quality (PQ) instruments. In this respect, the recently released edition 2 of the IEC 61869-1 standard extends the IT accuracy class concept up to 500 kHz. However, within the IEC 61869 standard family, guidelines for testing ITs only exist at power frequency, lacking information on the procedure and setup for assessing the frequency behaviour of ITs. This paper proposes a flexible architecture for generating currents with superimposed HFD. It involves the use of two current sources, one devoted to the generation of a fundamental tone at rated amplitude (theoretically up thousands of ampere) and frequency (DC or AC 50/60 Hz) and one for the superimposition of tones at reduced amplitude and frequencies in the HFD range. Through preliminary tests, the applicability of this proposed architecture has been experimentally validated and it is presented in this paper.

Keywords— Current Transformers, Instrument Transformers, High Frequency Distortion, Frequency Characterization, Power System Measurements, Medium Voltage.

I. INTRODUCTION

The growing utilization of switching devices (such as inverters, bulky power electronic converters, active filters,

etc.), both as loads and as part of generators, particularly in renewable energy sources, has led to a significant rise in conducted disturbances on grid voltage and current. This phenomenon extends to medium voltage (MV) levels and concerns frequencies up to hundreds of kilohertz, due to the harmonics of the switching frequency.

For instance, the conducted emissions from these new switching devices can disrupt Power Line Communication (PLC), a widely used communication method employed across electrical grids for essential functions like control and automation [1]. Such interferences compromise the integrity of transmitted data, potentially resulting in failures of critical grid operations [2]-[4]. High-frequency emissions from one device can easily couple with other devices, interfering with their control systems and potentially leading to malfunctions or complete failures. Furthermore, these emissions increase the current Root Mean Square (RMS) value, and this is associated with a more pronounced skin effect, resulting in temperature increase and consequent accelerated aging and reduced components lifespan.

Recently, great technological advancements in power converters, such as DC/DC (Direct Current), AC/DC (Alternating Current), and AC/AC, have taken place. New-generation power converters embed switching components like Silicon Carbide (SiC) Metal Oxide Semiconductor Field Effect Transistors (MOSFET) [5], [6], which enable higher switching frequencies, and this facilitate their direct integration into medium voltage (MV) power systems. Consequently, similar to the challenges encountered in low voltage (LV) grids [7]-[10], MV grids now are starting to face rising measurement requirements, which consist in enhanced

performance in terms of accuracy and broader frequency range.

These needs require improvements in Instrument Transformers (ITs), which are usually used as the first element in voltage and current measurement chains. Currently, existing standard IEC 61869 parts 1 edition 2 [11] specifies the accuracy limits of ITs at power frequency (i.e., 50/60 Hz) for MV and High Voltage (HV) grids and extend their requirements to frequencies up to 500 kHz. However, the in-force standards lack guidance on measurement methodologies, testing procedures, reference instrumentation, or uncertainty evaluation beyond power frequency. Consequently, manufacturers and calibration laboratories are left with significant discretion in assessing compliance with accuracy requirements above power frequency, thereby hindering end-users from effectively validating product performance.

In this scenario, the European Partnership in Metrology (EPM) 22NRM06 “ADMIT” project [12] has been recently funded. The project aims to establish suitable parameters for the definition of the accuracy of Voltage and Current Transformers (VTs and CTs), and the related measurement instrumentation, in the frequency range up to 150 kHz. To the best of the authors' knowledge, the traceable characterization of an MV VT or CT in the frequency range from power frequency up to 150 kHz, remains an open issue. Regarding CTs, generators capable of simultaneously generating the fundamental component (DC or AC 50/60 Hz) up to thousands of ampere and high-frequency components of reduced amplitude (up to hundreds of ampere), are not available in the market. Nevertheless, a current test facility was realised within the framework of the EPM 19NRM05 IT4PQ project, able to simultaneously generate the fundamental component up to thousands of amperes and high-frequency components up to hundreds of amperes [13]. However, its frequency range is limited to 9 kHz [14].

In this context, the activity presented in this paper, developed in the framework of ADMIT project, consists in the identification and experimental validation of a general architecture for the characterization of CTs up to 150 kHz in the presence of current representative of the real one that in with fundamental tone in MV range and superimposed tones at higher frequencies and reduced amplitude. In the paper, two initial applications of the proposed architecture are also presented, highlighting potential challenges to consider when designing and sizing a generation system based on the proposed architecture.

The structure of the paper is as follows: Section II provides a summary of scientific literature that deals with the topic addressed by the paper, in Section III the proposed generation architecture is described. Section IV and V present experimental setup and procedure and first results, respectively. Finally, Section VI draws the conclusions.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

Accurate measurement of voltage and current quantities is crucial for evaluating the actual state of the power network. However, the metrological performances of VTs and CTs are not always fully characterized in the presence of a fundamental waveform (AC or DC) with superimposed frequency components up to 150 kHz. A more accurate characterization involves the generation of waveforms similar to those found in actual working conditions, such as DC with

superimposed ripple or AC with superimposed frequency components. Some authors of this paper in [15] have proposed a novel generation setup to characterize MV VTs up to 20 kV at power frequency with distorted voltage waveforms with frequency components up to 10% of the fundamental tone and 150 kHz. Moreover, in [19], a calibration setup for accurate characterization of CTs with distorted waveforms up to 120 A and up to 10 kHz has been proposed.

However, currently, the main challenge for the characterization of CTs in real operating conditions is related to waveform generation up to thousands of ampere and up to hundreds of kilohertz. Several papers in the literature discuss current waveform generation techniques to characterize CTs for AC and DC applications. The generation setup developed in [16] is designed to characterize DC current sensors up to 600 A under realistic operating conditions for railway applications. The setup can characterize current sensors under various real conditions, including dynamic current profiles recorded during trips between underground train stations. Here, the aim is to provide traceable measurements with uncertainty analysis, which is essential for ensuring the accuracy of total electromagnetic field measurements in railway traction units. In [17] a novel methodology, called ALFO, for the traceable calibration of measuring systems with signals composed of DC with superimposed AC ripple, providing traceability for DC currents up to 100 A with AC ripple up to 1% of the DC in the frequency range 300 Hz-150 kHz, is presented. The measurement setup described in [14] has been developed for the metrological characterization of inductive and electronic CTs for AC applications at power frequencies up to 5 kA and frequencies up to 9 kHz. However, the test is performed here using a sinusoidal waveform with a frequency sweep up to 9 kHz. In [18] a traceable measuring system for AC current generation up to 2 kA at power frequency and up to 900 A up to 2 kHz was developed and characterized. In [20] a low-cost three-phase current generator has proposed. Here the current waveform is obtained by means power amplifiers to feed the primary side of current boost transformers.

The proposed architecture can generate AC current waveform with fundamental at power frequency and harmonic components up to 2 kHz. In [21] the generation architecture includes a waveform generator, power amplifier and transformers with the compensation filter. Here the challenge is related to design the compensation filter to generate accurately the desired reference waveform with spectral components up to 2 kHz.

Generating the current waveform for CTs characterization has some limitations. Firstly, the maximum amplitude of the generated current is limited to a few kA at the power frequency and tens of ampere up to 10 kHz due to measurement architecture, instrumentation, and implementation limits.

Secondly, in some cases, the maximum frequency is limited to 10 kHz, but usually, the frequency is limited to a few thousands of hertz due to the limit of current amplifier systems. Thirdly, not all measurement setups can generate distorted waveforms, such as fundamental components at power frequency or DC with superimposed frequency components up to 150 kHz; instead, a sinusoidal sweep is used. Here, a new general architecture is proposed to generate DC or fundamental at power frequency up to a thousand

ampere with superimposed frequency distortion up to 150 kHz and hundreds of amperes.

III. PROPOSED GENERATION ARCHITECTURE

The proposed general generation architecture is shown in Fig 1. It is based on the use of two different current sources: one is dedicated to the generation of Low Frequency (LF) DC or AC 50/60 Hz current with high-amplitude ($i_{LF}(t)$) while the other source is used to generate low-amplitude currents with frequencies up to several kilohertz ($i_{HF}(t)$). Two blocking elements are connected in series with the current generators when it is necessary to protect each generator from the current generated by the other one. Downstream of the filtering elements, the two currents are provided to the measurement branch which consists of the device under test (DUT) connected in series with the reference transducer (REF).

The scheme in Fig 1 is flexible and can be easily adopted in several cases and some of them are here recalled. Regarding the generation of the high amplitude currents $i_{LF}(t)$, two cases can be distinguished: DC currents and AC 50/60 Hz currents. For the DC case, high current levels can be obtained using a commercial generator, a transconductance amplifier or a generation system composed by a three-phase generator coupled with an autotransformer and a rectifier.

For the AC 50/60 Hz high current generation, the common adopted solutions are power transformers, commercial amplifier, power generator coupled with step up current transformers (CTs) [14].

For the generation of $i_{HF}(t)$ it is possible to use step up current transformers for MV application up to ~100 A suitably designed to have a flat frequency response within the desired band or a commercial transconductance amplifier.

Depending on the adopted solution, it may be necessary to appropriately design two blocking elements ($Block_{HF}$ and $Block_{LF}$) to ensure that the generated currents flow correctly only through the measurement branch (DUT+REF). The input quantities in the design process are the current levels and their frequency content, the input impedances of the two current generators and the impedance value of the series connection of the device under test and the reference one. The $Block_{HF}$ element is crucial for preventing HF currents from flowing into the $i_{LF}(t)$ generator. This can be achieved by offering high impedance to HF currents inserting into the circuit an inductance L . The impedance $Z_L = j\omega L$ in series with the input impedance of the LF generator should be at least ten times the impedance of the measurement branch. Similarly, the $Block_{LF}$

Fig 1: General scheme for the characterization of MV/HV current sensors under a current signal composed of high current at DC/power frequency with low amplitude and high frequency superimposed tones

block prevents LF currents from flowing into the HF generator by providing high impedance at 50/60 Hz, typically using a capacitor C . The capacitance value is chosen such that the resulting impedance $Z_C = 1/j\omega C$, in series with the impedance of the HF generator, is at least ten times higher than the impedance of the measurement branch.

IV. EXPERIMENTAL SETUP AND PROCEDURE

This Section introduces the experimental setup and the test procedure applied to assess the validity of the proposed architecture. The primary objective of the experimental activity presented here is to quantify the mutual impact between the two sources and the resulting current flowing into the measurement branch. In other words, the tests aim to evaluate how the presence of the LF generator affects the HF current in the measurement branch, and vice versa.

Starting from the general scheme presented in Section III, two cases are implemented:

- in the first case (*case A*), both $i_{LF}(t)$ and $i_{HF}(t)$ are generated using two transconductance amplifiers, each driven by an Arbitrary Waveforms Generator (AWG);
- in the second case (*case B*), the $i_{LF}(t)$ current is generated using a power amplifier coupled with a step-up CT whereas the $i_{HF}(t)$ is obtained by using a transconductance amplifier coupled with an AWG.

A. Generation and Measurement Setup

Considering the *Case A*, the used transconductance amplifiers are one Clarke Hess 8100 and one Clarke Hess 8200 [22], whose frequency-dependent impedance characteristics have been thoroughly measured, modelled and reported in [17]. The two transconductances are driven by two Keysight 33500 B AWGs (± 10 V, 120 MHz, THD lower than $300 \mu V/V$). Despite the dual-channel capability of the AWG, two separate AWGs are used to mitigate potential errors stemming from crosstalk phenomena among the channels. In this initial stage, synchronization of the two AWGs has not been implemented. The lack of synchronization does not represent an issue in terms of generation performance, which is the focus of the paper. Having synchronized sources can just simplify digital signal processing, enabling basic techniques such as DFT to extract phasors from the acquired signals.

For the *Case B*, the HF tones are generated using a Clarke Hess 8200 driven by a Keysight 33500 B. As for the LF fundamental component, two different step-up current transformers with different features have been used:

- CT₁: for MV application, 5/75 A/A, series inductance L_s of $19 \mu H$.
- CT₂: window type, 5/250 A/A, series inductance L_s of $0.5 \mu H$.

In Section V, which presents the experimental results, the generated current is measured in the measurement branch by the means of a reference shunt (REF) Fluke A40B (flat frequency response within 100 ppm up to 150 kHz) and a Fluke 8588 A multimeter used in digitizer mode with a sampling frequency of 2 MHz.

B. Test Procedure

As already mentioned, the main goal of the performed experimental activity is to quantify how each source affects the current in the measurement branch generated from the

Fig 2: $I_{HF}(f)$ desired current values (black dotted line) and measured under three configurations of $i_{LF}(t)$ generator: connected to the circuit and generating 0 A (blue line circle marker), connected to the circuit but set in standby mode (red line square marker) and disconnected from the circuit (yellow line asterisk marker).

other source when they are both active. To this end, the test procedure involves three steps:

1. the solely generation of $i_{LF}(t)$,
2. the solely generation of $i_{HF}(t)$ and
3. the simultaneous generation of the two currents $i_{LF}(t)$ and $i_{HF}(t)$.

The first two steps are indicated in the follow using the subscript ‘‘S’’ whereas for the third step the subscript ‘‘FHF’’ is used indicating that the resulting current is composed by a fundamental tone plus a high frequency component.

Experimental results are presented as the errors $\epsilon(f)$ associated with the current tone at frequency f , measured during the FHF test, compared to those measured during the single tone test S. Mathematically, the errors $\epsilon(f)$ are defined according to Equation 1:

$$\epsilon(f) = \frac{I_{FHF}(f) - I_S(f)}{I_n(f)} \quad (1)$$

Fig 3: errors $\epsilon(f)$ associated with HF tones measured when the $i_{LF}(t)$ generator is connected to the circuit and generating 40 A at 50 Hz, compared to the case when the $i_{LF}(t)$ generator is galvanically isolated.

where I_{FHF} and I_S are the RMS values of the current at frequency f measured under FHF and S test, respectively; I_n is the nominal RMS value of the current at frequency f . Since the only difference between the single-generation test S and the FHF test is the presence of both the generators, the index $\epsilon(f)$ quantifies the impact on the current tone at frequency f flowing into the measurement branch due to the presence of a second generator producing a current at different frequency and amplitude.

As regards the test points of the preliminary experimental activity here presented, the LF fundamental component is fixed at 50 Hz whereas the HF tone frequency ranges from 10 kHz to 150 kHz with amplitude equal to 10 % of the LF tone.

V. EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

In the following, the results of the two investigated configurations are discussed.

A. Connection of two transconductance amplifiers

Initially, steps 1 and 2 for exclusively generating one of the two currents are performed by setting the other generator in three different modes: 1) in standby and not connected to the circuit (galvanic insulation), 2) in standby but connected to the circuit (standby), 3) generating 0 A and connected to the circuit (operate 0 A). Considering the case of the solely generation of $i_{HF}(t)$, results related to these three configurations of the $i_{LF}(t)$ generator are provided in Fig 2. By the comparison of the curve obtained in standby mode and the one measured with galvanic insulation, it can be observed that deviations go from 170 μ A at 10 kHz to 1.5 mA at 150 kHz. Considering the case of the $i_{LF}(t)$ generator connected to the circuit and producing 0 A and the case of galvanic insulation of $i_{LF}(t)$ generator, higher deviations are observed with the increase of the frequency. Specifically, at 10 kHz deviation is lower than 200 μ A but it increases to 180 mA at 150 kHz.

The main result of this preliminary experiment consists in the verification that the transconductance amplifier exhibits different impedances and behaviors, depending on its configuration. The results shown in the following refer to the case in which the single test S is conducted by galvanically isolating the other generator.

Focusing on the comparison between FHF and S test, Fig. 3 provides the values of the errors $\epsilon(f)$ associated to the HF tones whereas for the 50 Hz current, the maximum error $\epsilon(50 \text{ Hz})$ is 50 μ A/A.

Looking at Fig. 3, it can be observed that the presence of $i_{LF}(t)$ generator has a low impact on the $i_{HF}(t)$ flowing into the measurement branch up to 50 kHz being the error $\epsilon(f)$ lower than 0.3 %. The 1 % threshold is reached at \sim 80 kHz whereas at 150 kHz the error increases to 4.50 %. As a general consideration, it can be observed that the error curve has a positive polarity for all the frequencies that, according to Equation 1, turns into higher values of HF currents in FHF test with respect to the HF current measured under single test S case.

To better investigate this phenomenon, the same test procedure is performed by selecting two different gains of the transconductance amplifier used to generate the 50 Hz $i_{LF}(t)$ current at 40 A: 10 S and 100 S. The comparison of the obtained results is provided in Table I where it can be observed that for 100 S gain case, error five times higher is

Fig 4: errors $\epsilon(f)$ associated with HF tones measured when the $i_{LF}(t)$ generator composed by power amplifier and CT₁ (blue line circle marker) and CT₂ (red line asterisk marker) are connected to the circuit and generating the fundamental tone, compared to the case when they are galvanically isolated.

measured at 150 kHz. The results of these experimental tests underscore that under the FHF test there is a coupling between the two generators that leads the LF generator to capture, amplify and generate HF components too.

However, between the two cases 10 S and 100 S, an increase in error by a factor of 10 is not observed even if the gain increases of ten times because the change in the transconductance gain also results in a modification of its output impedance.

In summary, the generation setup composed by two transconductance amplifiers poses no significant issues for the generation of the $i_{LF}(t)$ at 50 Hz with superimposed HF tones up to 80 kHz, with errors lower than 1 %. However, when frequencies increase from 80 kHz to 150 kHz, the coupling between the generators leads to a rise in the error $\epsilon(f)$ of up to 4.5 %.

B. Connection of a step-up current transformer and a transconductance amplifier

As said in Section IV, this configuration is setup with two different CTs. For both, experimental results are presented in Fig. 4 for the HF tones; instead, errors lower than 500 $\mu\text{A}/\text{A}$ are measured at 50 Hz. As it can be observed, the different specifications of the two CTs result in errors $\epsilon(f)$ that differ significantly, by an order of magnitude. For CT₁ $\epsilon(f)$ is always lower than -1 % whereas for CT₂ goes from -9.7 % at 10 kHz to -5.7 % at 150 kHz.

However, for both the cases the errors are always negative, which means that $I_S(f) > I_{FHF}(f)$. Therefore, the connection of the $i_{LF}(t)$ generator to the circuit causes part of the $i_{HF}(t)$ current to flow through the $i_{LF}(t)$ generator instead of the measurement branch.

This phenomenon is inversely proportional to the current frequency because, as the frequency increases, the output impedance of the step-up transformer, which can be approximated as $Z=j\omega L_s$, also increases.

Basing on this consideration, it is clear why the errors in HF current tones are much lower when CT₁ is used as a step-up transformer for generating 50 Hz current with respect to CT₂. In fact, L_s of CT₁ has a value about 38 time higher than the one of CT₂.

TABLE I. IMPACT OF THE GAIN OF THE TRANSCONDUCTANCE USED TO GENERATE 50 HZ CURRENT ON THE HF TONES

Frequency (kHz)	ϵ (%)	
	10 S	100 S
10	0.000	-0.042
20	0.042	0.022
50	0.278	0.493
100	1.347	3.053
125	2.468	7.130
150	4.496	21.141

Additionally, CT₁ has a significantly lower turns ratio than CT₂, with the two being in a ratio of $\sim 1:15$. The turns ratio T is a crucial parameter because the output resistance and inductance of the power amplifier used to drive the CTs, are reflected to the CT secondary side with a factor equal to $1/T^2$. Therefore, since the same power amplifier is used in both cases, the impedance of the amplifier is reflected to the secondary side of CT₁ weighted by $(5/75)^2$, while for CT₂ it is weighted by $(5/250)^2$.

To improve the performance of the generation system based on the use of the CT₂, it is possible to introduce an inductive blocking element (Block_{HF}) into the circuit to reduce the $\epsilon(f)$ error associated to the high-frequency current tones. Regarding the blocking element Block_{LF}, in the case analysed in this paper, its necessity is not emphasized because the transconductance amplifier used to generate the HF current has a capacitive input impedance able to provide high impedance at 50 Hz [22] [17].

VI. CONCLUSIONS

The growing presence of HFD in MV grids is driving the necessity of accurate characterizing ITs included in the measurement chains of these disturbances. In this context, the paper proposed a flexible generation system for testing CTs in the presence of realistic signals, consisting of a high-current fundamental tone with superimposed disturbances at reduced amplitude and high frequency. Through experimental tests, two different configurations of the proposed generation setup were tested: one based on the use of two transconductance amplifiers and one based on the use of step up transformers and transconductance amplifiers. In both the cases, feasibility was demonstrated. The case based on the use of step-up CTs has highlighted that in some situations it can be necessary the insertion of blocking elements, specifically designed, into the circuit in order to improve the performance of the generation system. Future activities will be aimed at 1) experimenting other configurations of the proposed generation architecture, 2) designing and incorporating blocking elements into the circuit to quantify the improvement achieved through their use; and 3) using the generation system to characterize commercial CTs.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

The project 22NRM06 ADMIT has received funding from the European Partnership on Metrology, co-financed by the European Union's Horizon Europe Research and Innovation Programme and by the Participating States.

REFERENCES

- [1] "IEC 62488 Standard family, "Power line communication systems for power utility applications".

- [2] P. Kotsampopoulos et al., "EMC Issues in the Interaction Between Smart Meters and Power-Electronic Interfaces," in *IEEE Transactions on Power Delivery*, vol. 32, no. 2, pp. 822-831, April 2017.
- [3] S. K. Rönnerberg, A. G. -d. Castro, M. H. J. Bollen, A. Moreno-Munoz and E. Romero-Cadaval, "Supraharmonics from power electronics converters," *2015 9th International Conference on Compatibility and Power Electronics (CPE)*, Costa da Caparica, Portugal, 2015, pp. 539-544.
- [4] Sarah K. Rönnerberg, Math H.J. Bollen, Hortensia Amaris, Gary W. Chang, Irene Y.H. Gu, Łukasz H. Kocewiak, Jan Meyer, Magnus Olofsson, Paulo F. Ribeiro, Jan Desmet, "On waveform distortion in the frequency range of 2kHz–150kHz—Review and research challenges", *Electric Power Systems Research*, vol. 150, 2017, pp. 1-10.
- [5] Y. Xia, J. Roy and R. Ayyanar, "Optimal Variable Switching Frequency Scheme to Reduce Loss of Single-Phase Grid-Connected Inverter With Unipolar and Bipolar PWM," in *IEEE Journal of Emerging and Selected Topics in Power Electronics*, vol. 9, no. 1, pp. 1013-1026, Feb. 2021.
- [6] "Z. Lu et al., "Medium Voltage Soft-Switching DC/DC Converter With Series-Connected SiC MOSFETs," in *IEEE Transactions on Power Electronics*, vol. 36, no. 2, pp. 1451-1462, Feb. 2021.
- [7] E. O. A. Larsson, M. H. J. Bollen, M. G. Wahlberg, C. M. Lundmark and S. K. Rönnerberg, "Measurements of High-Frequency (2–150 kHz) Distortion in Low-Voltage Networks," in *IEEE Transactions on Power Delivery*, vol. 25, no. 3, pp. 1749-1757, July 2010.
- [8] V. Khokhlov, J. Meyer, A. Grevenner, T. Busatto and S. Rönnerberg, "Comparison of Measurement Methods for the Frequency Range 2–150 kHz (Supraharmonics) Based on the Present Standards Framework," in *IEEE Access*, vol. 8, pp. 77618-77630, 2020.
- [9] S. T. Y. Alfalahi et al., "Supraharmonics in Power Grid: Identification, Standards, and Measurement Techniques," in *IEEE Access*, vol. 9, pp. 103677-103690, 2021.
- [10] A. J. Collin, A. Delle Femine, C. Landi, R. Langella, M. Luiso and A. Testa, "The Role of Supply Conditions on the Measurement of High-Frequency Emissions," in *IEEE Transactions on Instrumentation and Measurement*, vol. 69, no. 9, pp. 6667-6676, Sept. 2020.
- [11] IEC 61869 standard family "Instrument transformers".
- [12] EPM 22NRM06 ADMIT, https://www.euramet.org/news-events-seg/details-news?tx_news_pi1%5Baction%5D=detail&tx_news_pi1%5Bcontroller%5D=News&tx_news_pi1%5Bnews%5D=1743&cHash=3dee4ab74ccbad5c668e69d243abf8fc [Available online on 6 June 2024].
- [13] "Final Publishable Report Measurement methods and test procedures for assessing accuracy of instrument transformers for power quality measurements (19NRM05)", https://www.euramet.org/download?tx_eurametfiles_download%5Baction%5D=download&tx_eurametfiles_download%5Bcontroller%5D=File&tx_eurametfiles_download%5Bfiles%5D=49678&tx_eurametfiles_download%5Bidentifier%5D=%252Fdocs%252FEFMRP%252FJR%252FJRP_Summaries_2019%252FNormative%252F19NRM05_Final_Publishable_Report.pdf&cHash=803a3f062c491dc3ee24b2ab621d47d (Available online on 7 June 2024)
- [14] Y. Chen, A. Dubowik and E. Mohns, "Reference system for current sensor calibrations at power frequency and for wideband frequencies," *2022 20th International Conference on Harmonics & Quality of Power (ICHQP)*, Naples, Italy, 2022, pp. 1-6, doi: 10.1109/ICHQP53011.2022.9808745.
- [15] G. Crotti et al., "Characterization of Voltage Transformers for MV Applications Up to 150 kHz - A Preliminary Study," *2023 IEEE 13th International Workshop on Applied Measurements for Power Systems (AMPS)*, Bern, Switzerland, 2023, pp. 01-05, doi: 10.1109/AMPS59207.2023.10297174.
- [16] H. E. Van Den Brom, R. Van Leeuwen, e R. Hornecker, «Characterization of DC Current Sensors With AC Distortion for Railway Applications», *IEEE Trans. Instrum. Meas.*, vol. 68, fasc. 6, pp. 2084–2090, giu. 2019, doi: 10.1109/TIM.2019.2898014.
- [17] D. Giordano, A. Delle Femine, D. Gallo, e D. Signorino, «Traceability for AC Ripple Over DC Current», *IEEE Transactions on Instrumentation and Measurement*, vol. 73, pp. 1–9, 2024, doi: 10.1109/TIM.2024.3385034.
- [18] M. Ohlrogge, R. Hönninger, M. Kult, e S. Jurgeit, «Setup of a Broadband High-Current Measuring System for the Traceable Calibration of Current Transducers», *IEEE Transactions on Instrumentation and Measurement*, vol. 72, pp. 1–8, 2023, doi: 10.1109/TIM.2022.3232664.
- [19] G. Crotti et al., «Calibration of Current Transformers in distorted conditions», presentato al *Journal of Physics: Conference Series*, 2018. doi: 10.1088/1742-6596/1065/5/052033.
- [20] M. Faifer, C. Laurano, R. Ottoboni, e S. Toscani, «Development of a Low-Cost Three-Phase Current Generator for Testing Current Transformers», in *2023 IEEE 13th International Workshop on Applied Measurements for Power Systems (AMPS)*, set. 2023, pp. 01–06. doi: 10.1109/AMPS59207.2023.10297152.
- [21] L. Cristaldi, M. Faifer, C. Laurano, R. Ottoboni, S. Toscani, e M. Zaroni, «A Low-Cost Generator for Testing and Calibrating Current Transformers», *IEEE Transactions on Instrumentation and Measurement*, vol. 68, fasc. 8, pp. 2792–2799, ago. 2019, doi: 10.1109/TIM.2018.2870264.
- [22] D. T. Hess and K. K. Clarke, "Evaluation of 100 Ampere 100 kHz transconductance amplifiers", *Conf. Precis. Electromagn. Meas. Dig.*, pp. 611-612, Jul. 1998.